

Diabetes and Dental Disease : A Two-Way Street

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Received on: 28 - 05 - 2025; Accepted on: 04 - 06 - 2025; Published on : 07-07- 2025

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Abstract

Diabetes mellitus is the most common endocrine disease and can be classified into type 1, type 2, gestational, and other specific types. Type 1 diabetes is often autoimmune in origin, typically emerging in childhood, and requires lifelong insulin therapy. Type 2 diabetes, more prevalent in adults and increasingly in children, is related to insulin resistance and often linked with obesity. Diabetes manifests systemically and has significant oral health implications such as xerostomia, periodontal disease, increased caries risk, and poor wound healing. Proper diagnosis involves plasma glucose tests and HbA1c levels. Management includes lifestyle changes, pharmacologic therapy with insulin or metformin, and careful dental care planning. Dentists must assess glycemic control before procedures, prevent hypoglycemic episodes during treatment, and ensure post-operative care to minimize complications. Interdisciplinary coordination is essential for optimal outcomes in diabetic patients, particularly in managing dental and systemic health.

Keyword : Diabetes Mellitus, Dental Operatory, Endocrine Disease, Oral Menifestation.

Introduction

Endocrine and metabolic diseases are one of the common contemporary human afflictions, particularly in the United States and other countries with generous nutrition and screening programs for high-risk individuals.

Endocrine disease refers to a group of medical conditions that affect the endocrine system, which is responsible for producing hormones that regulate various bodily functions. These disorders can be caused by a variety of factors, including hormonal imbalances, genetic factors, and tumors . Some common types of endocrine diseases include Diabetes mellitus, Hyperthyroidism, Hypothyroidism, Cushing disease, Addison disease, Acromegaly etc.¹

Classification

There are many different types of endocrine disorders. Diabetes is the most common endocrine disorder.

Other Endocrine Disorders Include²

Adrenal insufficiency. The adrenal gland releases too little of the hormone cortisol and sometimes, aldosterone. Symptoms

include fatigue, stomach upset, dehydration, and skin changes. Addison's disease is a type of adrenal insufficiency.

Cushing's disease. Overproduction of a pituitary gland hormone leads to an overactive adrenal gland. A similar condition called Cushing's syndrome may occur in people, particularly children, who take high doses of corticosteroid medications.

Gigantism (acromegaly) and other growth hormone problems. If the pituitary gland produces too much growth hormone, a child's bones and body parts may grow abnormally fast.

Dwarfism, If growth hormone levels are too low, a child can stop growing in height.

Hyperthyroidism. The thyroid gland produces too much thyroid hormone, leading to weight loss, fast heart rate, sweating, and nervousness. The most common cause for an

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Website : www.healtalk.in

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How to cite this article : Datta et al. - Diabetes and Dental Disease : A Two-Way Street, AJ OCD-HT 2025

overactive thyroid is an autoimmune disorder called Grave's disease.

Hypothyroidism. The thyroid gland does not produce enough thyroid hormone, leading to fatigue, constipation, dry skin, and depression. The underactive gland can cause slowed development in children. Some types of hypothyroidism are present at birth.

Hypopituitarism. The pituitary gland releases little or no hormones. It may be caused by a number of different diseases. Women with this condition may stop getting their periods.

Multiple endocrine neoplasia I and II (MEN I and MEN II). These rare, genetic conditions are passed down through families. They cause tumors of the parathyroid, adrenal, and thyroid glands, leading to overproduction of hormones.

Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS). Overproduction of androgens interfere with the development of eggs and their release from the female ovaries. PCOS is a leading cause of infertility.

Precocious puberty. Abnormally early puberty that occurs when glands tell the body to release sex hormones too soon in life.

Diabetes Mellitus

"Diabetes mellitus is a group of endocrine diseases characterized by hyperglycemia resulting from defects in insulin secretion, insulin action, or both, leading to abnormalities in fat, carbohydrate, and protein metabolism"(American Diabetes Association 2014a).³

Epidemiology

Global

The most recent statistics (2010) indicate that in the United state approximately 215,000 children younger than 20 years old have either type 1 or type 2 diabetes. (Centers for disease control and prevention, 2010).

The odds are higher for African-American and Hispanic children-nearly 50% of them will develop diabetes.

India

It is estimated that childhood diabetes accounts for around 5% of total population of diabetics. In India alone, there are likely to be about 4,00,000 infants and children with this disease.

Diabetes mellitus (DM) can occur in children at any age, but 40% of children diagnosed are between 10 to 14 years old and 60% are between 15 to 19years old.⁴

Girls are 1.3 to 1.7 times more likely to develop type 2 diabetes than boys.

Classification

A. According to "The american diabetes association standards of medical care for diabetes 2021":⁵

1. Type 1 Diabetes - Autoimmune destruction of insulin secreting β -cells leading to insulin deficiency.
2. Type 2 Diabetes - Inadequate insulin secretion that cannot overcome the existing degree of insulin

resistance.

3. Gestational diabetes - Diabetes diagnosed in the second or third trimester of pregnancy that is not clearly overt diabetes.
 4. Monogenic diabetes syndromes - Neonatal diabetes, maturity-onset diabetes of the young [MODY].
 5. Disease of the exocrine pancreas - Cystic fibrosis, pancreatitis, pancreatectomy.
 6. Medication induced- Glucocorticoids, treatment of HIV/AIDS, immunosuppressants, chemotherapeutic agents
- B. "WHO" classification of diabetes based on etiology (2019):⁶
1. Type 1 diabetes (Insulin dependent diabetes mellitus)
 2. Type 2 diabetes (Non insulin dependent diabetes mellitus)
 3. Hybrid forms of diabetes
 - a. Slowly evolving immune-mediated diabetes of adults
 - b. Ketosis prone type 2 diabetes
 4. Other specific types
 - a. Monogenic diabetes
 - Monogenic defects of β -cell function
 - Monogenic defects in insulin action
 - b. Diseases of the exocrine pancreas
 - c. Endocrine disorders
 - d. Drug- or chemical-induced
 - e. Infections
 - f. Uncommon specific forms of immune-mediated diabetes
 - g. Other genetic syndromes sometimes associated with diabetes
 5. Unclassified diabetes

This category should be used temporarily when there is not a clear diagnostic category especially close to the time of diagnosis of diabetes.
 6. Hyperglycemia first detected during pregnancy
 - Diabetes mellitus in pregnancy
 - Gestational diabetes mellitus

Clinical Features of Type 1 And Type 2 Diabetes^{7,8}

- A. Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus (Insulin dependent diabetes mellitus)-Type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) comprises several diseases of the pancreatic β cells which lead to an absolute insulin deficiency. Less common (10%) usually younger than 30 years. This is usually considered to be the result of an autoimmune destruction of the pancreatic β cells (type 1A). Some patients with T1DM with no evidence of β cell autoimmunity have underlying defects in insulin secretion often from inherited defects in pancreatic β cell glucose sensing and from other genetic or acquired diseases.

The onset of symptoms is rapid and Patients present in two ways:

1. Classic triad- polyuria, polydipsia and polyphagia in association with weight loss.
2. Ketoacidosis-some patients present with diabetic ketoacidosis following acute infection or surgery or without any apparent cause. If ketoacidosis is severe patients may develop mental apathy, confusion and may lapse into coma called diabetic ketotic coma. Patient will die if left untreated.

B. Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus(Non insulin dependent diabetes mellitus)-Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is by far the more common type of diabetes and is characterized by insulin resistance resulting from defects in the action of insulin on its target tissues (muscle, liver, and fat), but complicated by varying and usually progressive failure of beta cells' insulin secretory capacity. More common (90%) usually seen in obese and older. Most patients with T2DM in the US and Europe are overweight or obese, however in India and China, most T2DM patients have a lean body mass index (BMI), albeit with increased visceral and hepatic fat.

1. Eye- Recurrent styes, Frequent change of glasses due to error of refraction, Visual impairment due to premature development of cataract.
2. GI tract- Chronic diarrhoea, malabsorption, gastroparesis.
3. Cardiovascular- Ischaemic heart disease, hypertension, peripheral vascular diseases.
4. Skin-Multiple boils, carbuncles, abscesses, non healing wound, mucocutaneous candidiasis.
5. Respiratory- Pneumonias, lung abscess, tuberculosis etc.

C. Monogenic Diabetes

Monogenic forms of diabetes are characterized by impaired secretion of insulin from pancreatic β cells caused by a single gene mutation. These forms comprise a genetically heterogenous group of diabetes including, maturity onset diabetes of the young (MODY), permanent or transient neonatal diabetes, and mitochondrial diabetes. MODY is the most common form of monogenic diabetes, with autosomal dominant transmission of one of several genes encoding a primary defect in insulin secretion.

D. Neonatal diabetes mellitus (NDM)

A special form of genetic diabetes is neonatal diabetes mellitus (NDM) and diabetes that manifests within the first 6 months of life. Clinically, they are classified into 2 subgroups: transient (TNDM) and permanent (PNDM) neonatal diabetes mellitus. For diagnosis of neonatal diabetes or diabetes manifestation up to and including the sixth month of life.

Oral Manifestation

1. **Xerostomia** - People with diabetes experience salivary dysfunction, which can lead to decreased salivary flow and change in saliva composition. The estimated universal prevalence of xerostomia among diabetic patients ranges

between 34% and 51%.⁹

2. **Dental caries** - Diabetic patients are susceptible to the development of new and recurrent dental caries. Reduced cleansing and buffering capacity of the saliva, increase of carbohydrate in the saliva, and increased level of oral yeasts, mutans streptococci and lactobacilli can lead to an increase in the incidence of tooth decay. In addition, chronic hyperglycemia may cause irreversible pulpitis leading to pulp necrosis
3. **Periodontal disease** - Poor glycemic control can be associated with the outbreak and progression of gingivitis, periodontitis, and alveolar bone loss. Periodontal disease has been reported with increased incidence and prevalence in patients with type 1 and 2 diabetes. Prevalence of severe periodontitis in diabetic patients compared to non diabetics has been found to be 59.6%.¹⁰
4. **Oral infections** - Patients with diabetes are more susceptible to the development of various oral infections including fungal and bacterial infections. Decreased salivary flow rate and the absence of its antimicrobial effects can cause these infections. In addition, an impaired defense mechanism and poor metabolic control may play an important role in developing infection. Oral candidiasis is an opportunistic fungal infection. The prevalence of that is increasing, as it is one of the most common fungal infections. Higher candida colonization rates were reported in patients with diabetes type 1 when compared to type 2.
5. **Burning mouth** - Burning sensation or dysesthesia in the oral cavity of diabetic patients is attributed to poor glycemic control, metabolic alterations in oral mucosa, angiopathy, candida infection, and neuropathy. Neuropathic pain in these patients can be manifested as burning, tingling, or even as electric shock or stabbing sensation that these symptoms may be very debilitating.
6. **Taste dysfunction** - Taste dysfunction can occur in patients with poorly controlled diabetes. In a crosssectional study, among diabetic or prediabetic patients, 5.7% had a sweet taste disorder and 8.6% had a salt taste disorder . Salivary dysfunction can cause altered taste sensation or raise of detection thresholds. Neuropathy also increases the threshold of taste.
7. **Oral mucosa alterations** - Some oral mucosa alterations such as coated and fissured tongue, geographic tongue, recurrent aphthous stomatitis, and some premalignant lesions including lichen planus can be associated with diabetes . OLP occurs more frequently in patients with type 1 diabetes compared to type 2, because type 1 diabetes is considered an autoimmune disease, and OLP has an underlying autoimmune mechanism .(Fig:1)
8. **Poor wound healing** - Delayed healing of soft and hard tissues in diabetic patients is a well-known complication during oral surgeries. Based on some studies, effective factors in the prolonged wound healing of these patients include

delayed vascularization, diminished blood flow and hypoxia, a reduction in innate immunity, decreased growth factor production, and psychological stress.¹¹

Fig 1-Oral manifestation of diabetes A-Lichen Planus, B- Fissured Tongue

Diagnosis

Diabetes mellitus is characterized by recurrent or persistent hyperglycemia, and is diagnosed by demonstrating any one of the following:⁷

1. Plasma glucose level ≥ 11.1 mmol/L (200 mg/dl) 2 hour after a 75 g oral glucose load as in a glucose tolerance test.
2. Fasting plasma glucose level 7.0 mmol/L (126mg/dl).
3. Glycated haemoglobin (Hb A1C) $\geq 6.5\%$.

Management

- A. Non-pharmacological management- lifestyle modification can be achieved by increasing physical activity and dietary modification.
- B. Pharmacological therapy-
 1. Mild to asymptomatic children who have been on medical nutritional therapy and failed to comply exercise as well, should be on metformin therapy.
 2. Symptomatic children with diabetic ketoacidosis and infection should be given insulin for immediated control, once stabilized can be shifted to metformin.
 3. Moderate to severe type 2diabetes drug of choice for children is insulin and metformin. However many other antidiabetic drugs are available, e.g. Sulphonylureas, glinides, thiazolidinediones but are not approved for children below 18 years.¹²

C. Dosages

i.	Insulin	Subcutaneous insulin doses in children with newly diagnosed type 1 diabetes vary widely from 0.2 units/kg/day to 0.8 units/kg/day
ii.	Metformin Solution	Children 10 to 16 years, at first 5ml two times a day taken with meal. if needed dose will increase by 5ml weekly but the dose is usually not more than 20 ml.

Table 1- Dosages of Drugs For Diabetes

Dental Management

• **Pre-operatively⁷**

1. History - Detailed case history should be taken before

starting of any treatment.

Unknown diabetic patient

- a. Any dental patient whose condition remain undiagnosed but has the cardinal symptoms of diabetes should be referred to physician.
- b. Patients with findings that may suggest diabetes should be referred to a clinical laboratory or a physician for screening test.

Known diabetic patient

- a. All patients with diabetes must be identified by history, and the type of medical treatment they are receiving must be established.
 - b. The type of diabetes should be determined and the presence of complications noted.
 - c. If diabetes is well controlled, all dental procedures can be performed without special precautions before starting the procedure verify that the patients have take medication and diet as usual.
 - d. If diabetes is poorly controlled i. e fasting blood glucose < 70 mg/dl or > 200 mg/dl and any complications (renal disease, congestive heart failure, symptomatic angina, cardiac and blood pressure is high) all elective dental procedures should be postponed. Provide only emergency care and consult patient physician.
2. Appointment - Morning appointments are preferable as endogenous cortisol level are generally high at this time.
 3. Others - A source of glucose should be present in the dental office to avoid hypoglycemic attack or hypoglycaemia.

• **During Treatment¹³**

- a. Duration of treatment should be small.
- b. Minimal trauma during any dental procedure.
Emergency during treatment -A major goal in dental management of diabetes is to prevent insulin shock or hypoglycemia and hyperglycemia.

Hypoglycemia - Hypoglycemia is often defined by a plasma glucose concentration below 70 mg/dL; however, signs and symptoms may not occur until plasma glucose concentrations drop below 55 mg/dL..

- a. Sign and symptoms of hypoglycaemia – Confusion, Restlessness, Sweating, Tachycardia, Tremors, Thirst, Flushed skin etc. As soon as such sign and symptoms are present the dentist should check the glucose by the glucometer.
- b. Management
 - i. Establishing airway ,breathing, circulation.
 - ii. Place the patient in the supine position and turn on the fans or conditioner.
 - iii. If the patient is conscious and able to take food by mouth then give 15g of the carbohydrate in the following form, orange juice, 3-4 tablespoon of sugar ,a small amount of sweet/honey can be placed in buccal fold.

- iv. In unconscious patient take 20-30ml of the dextrose in 50% of the concentration or 1mg of the glucagon IV/IM.

The sign and symptoms should be resolved in 10 to 15 mins. The normal blood glucose level is confirmed by the glucometer before the patients leaves.

Hyperglycaemia- Hyperglycemia is blood glucose greater than 125 mg/dL while fasting and greater than 180 mg/dL 2 hours postprandial.

- a. Sign and symptoms of hyperglycaemia - This condition is much less common than hypoglycaemia. Signs and symptoms are excessive urination, Fruity breath, Bradycardia, Pale and cold clammy skin etc. As soon as such sign and symptoms are present the dentist should check the glucose by the glucometer. Hypoglycaemia and can eventually lead to coma.
- b. Management
- i First recognize problem if there was any lack of response to sensory stimulation then discontinue dental treatment and activate office emergency team.
- ii. Establishing airway, breathing, circulation.
- iii. Place the patient in the supine position with legs elevated.
- iv. Definitive care- Summon emergency medical service .

• **Post operative period**

1. If the patients in not able to eat after the dental procedure so he/she is recommended to eat soft food or liquid. Consult patient physician for the post operative diet plan.
2. Diabetic patients have poor wound healing ,there for they are at greater risk for developing infections. Antibiotic coverage is necessary for the patients undergoing extensive dental surgical procedure.

General Health Care Instruction

1. Patients should follow good home care
2. Good glucose control and take medications as prescribed.

Conclusion

Diabetes mellitus significantly impacts both systemic and oral health, requiring early diagnosis, proper medical management, and coordinated dental care. Effective glycemic control and interdisciplinary collaboration are essential to prevent complications and ensure comprehensive care for diabetic patients.

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